

Acrida sp., *Acrotylus humbertianus* Sauss, *Atractomorpha acutipennis* (Guer.), *Calliptamus* sp., *Catantops pinguis* Stal., *Chroedicus illustris* Wlk., *Eyprepocnemis plorans* Charp, *Shirakiacris shirakii* I. Bol., *Oedaleus abruptus* Thunb., and *Truxalis grandis* Dirsh are also found on rice but in low numbers.

Grasshoppers are more serious in the rice nurseries where young nymphs accumulate in large numbers and damage the seedlings. In some cases almost the whole of a nursery plot is destroyed. Plowing of fields and digging of embankments during winter seem good control measures because they destroy most of the egg pods. ❧

Insecticidal control of the brown planthopper in the field

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Field studies on the efficacy of insecticides against the rice brown

planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* showed that the maximum reduction of insect numbers occurred in plots treated with carbofuran 3% G (2.25 kg a.i./ha), followed by that in plots treated with methamidophos (0.1% spray), Phorate (2.25 kg a.i./ha), and phoxim (0.05% spray). In general, mephosfolan 10% G was found to be ineffective. ❧

Effect of paddy-water and foliar applications of insecticides on brown planthopper populations 9–12 weeks after transplanting, Annamalainagar, India, kuruvai, 1973.

Treatment ^a	Application rate (kg a.i./ha)	Planthoppers ^b (no./hill)					Change from control level (%)
		9 wk	10 wk	11 wk	12 wk	Mean	
Carbofuran granules	0.75	0	61	27	28	29	- 67
	1.50	0	0	0	44	11	- 88
	2.25	0	0	0	0	0	- 100
Phorate granules	0.75	5	39	121	143	77	- 13
	1.50	6	33	153	156	87	- 2
	2.25	3	13	62	71	37	- 58
Mephosfolan granules	0.75	2	58	160	128	87	- 2
	1.50	3	132	123	125	96	+ 8
	2.25	4	20	122	122	92	+ 4
Methamidophos spray	0.025%	3	17	62	61	41	- 54
	0.05%	4	2	111	88	51	- 42
	0.1%	7	18	46	76	37	- 58
Phoxim spray	0.025%	4	37	128	131	73	- 17
	0.05%	2	45	78	76	50	- 43
	0.1%	4	77	99	92	68	- 23
Control	-	13	48	132	143	89

^aChemicals applied on 15th and 45th days after transplanting; treatments significant at 1% level (C.D. = 1.741).

^bAv. of 20 hills.

Research on pests of rice in Malawi (Central Africa)

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From 1971 until 1975 a research project was conducted to determine the relative importance of various insect pests of rice in Malawi.

The most numerous insect pest of rice is the stem borer *Diopsis thoracica* Westwood (Diptera; Diopsidae). Other diopsids are unimportant. Lepidopterous

stem borers, such as *Maliarpha separatella* Rag., *Chilo partellus* (Swinh.), *Chilo diffusilineus* (de Joannis), *Sesamia calamistas* (Hamps.), *Schoenobius* sp., and *Thopeutis* spp., are of little importance, since they are controlled by many parasitoids. At the end of prolonged rainy seasons, fields planted late were attacked by the rice gall midge *Orseola oryzae* (Wood-Mason).

Three larval parasitoids kept that pest under control. Several outbreaks of the rice beetle *Trichispa sericea* (Guer.), occurred in rice fields with high water

levels. In the 1972–73 season several hectares of nurseries were destroyed by this species. However, parasitoids usually kept the beetle under control. Other pests of minor importance were lepidopterous defoliators such as *Nymphula depunctalis* (Guen.), *Spodoptera cilium* Guen., *Diacrisia scortillum* (Wllgr.), *Borbo borbonica* (Boisd.), *Grammodes geometrica* F., *Mythimna* sp. and *Brachmia* sp., the green rice bug *Nezara viridula* (L.), and the mole cricket *Gryllotalpa africana* (P. de Beauv.).

Most of the Lepidoptera were identified by Dr. P. E. S. Whalley and Dr. I. W. B. Nye of the British Museum (Natural History).

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Pest management and control

WEEDS

Weed competition in transplanted rice

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To study the effect of various weeds in season-long competition with IR34, the desired weed species were sown with the rice at transplanting. Then at regular intervals all weeds, except the species under study, were removed.

All weeds except *Salvinia natans* caused yield losses (see table). The losses ranged from 19% (with competition from *Marsilea minuta*) to 43% (with competition from *Fimbristylis* sp. and *Echinochloa colona*). Losses were greater when competition was from more than one weed. The greatest loss (55%) occurred in the unweeded check plot, where all the tested weed species and the natural weed population competed simultaneously against rice.